

Studies in Silicic Acid Gels. Part III. Effect of Non-electrolytes on the Time of Setting of the Gel-forming Mixtures.

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It has been shown in the previous communication that when solutions of acidic ammonium acetate or acetic acid and sodium silicate are mixed together, a colloidal solution of silicic acid is first formed in the mixture; the charge on the colloidal particles is positive or negative according to the acidic or alkaline nature of the medium. The gel is probably formed by the coagulation of the colloidal solution.

It is well known that non-electrolytes cause the coagulation of many negatively and positively charged colloidal solutions and also exert a retarding or accelerating influence on the coagulation of sols by electrolytes. Gel-forming mixtures contain an undialyzed sol of silicic acid (*cf.* Part II) and the addition of non-electrolytes to these mixtures may influence the coagulation of the sol by the electrolytes present in the mixture.

The present investigation was, therefore, undertaken to examine the behaviour of non-electrolytes on the time of setting of the gel-forming mixtures. The silicic acid gels studied in this investigation have been prepared by Bhatnagar and Mathur's method (*Kolloid. Z.*, 1922, 30, 368) as well as by mixing solution of sodium silicate with various organic and inorganic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A stock solution of sodium silicate (Na_2O , 2SiO_2) was prepared as described in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 659) and the 4 per cent. solutions, used throughout this investigation, were prepared from it by dilution, each time any series of observations

were made. A solution of 4 per cent. silica content was titrated with 0.66 *N*-acids. In all the experiments described in this paper, gels were prepared with acids above or below this concentration. Merck's pure acids were used throughout and were carefully standardised.

The effect of pyridine, alcohols and acetone has been studied. The effect of pyridine has been studied more elaborately than that of other non-electrolytes because of its interesting behaviour.

Solutions of sodium silicate containing the non-electrolytes and of acids or of acidic ammonium acetate were mixed together by pouring the contents from one test-tube to another. But it was found that solutions were not thoroughly mixed in this way; often local flocculation took place and a uniform gel was not obtained. To overcome this difficulty the device described below was used.

A short limb of a glass tube was fused to a longer limb of glass at an acute angle. The two solutions were introduced into the two limbs and the open end was closed by a rubber cork. The contents were mixed by a rapidly inverting the arrangement a number of times. The stop-watch was started simultaneously with the mixing.

Solutions after thorough mixing were transferred to the cell and the deflections of the galvanometer were noted at different intervals of time. The time of the setting of the gel was determined from the time-deflection curves in the manner pointed out in Part I. (*loc. cit.*)

Effect of Pyridine.

Different amounts of pyridine were added to 5 c.c. of the sodium silicate solution and this was mixed with 5 c.c. of varying concentrations of ammonium acetate and hydrochloric acid in the manner described above. In each of these experiments the total volume of the mixture was therefore more than 10 c.c. The dilution factor was not taken into consideration as the effect of the added non-electrolyte was predominantly coagulating.

The results obtained are described in the following tables. The symbols employed represent

Q = c.c. of pyridine added to 10 c.c. of the mixture;

t = time of setting of the gel ;

A = scattering of light, $D_i - D_t$ (where D_i and D_t are the deflections initially and at the time t) in terms of deflections in mm. of the galvanometer,

TABLE I.

Concentration of NH_4Ac = 5 per cent.					
<i>Reaction alkaline.</i>					
Q ...	0	0.1	0.3	0.6	1.0
t ...	7	6	4½	3½	3
A ...	19	21	22	22	28

TABLE II.

Concentration of NH_4Ac = 20 per cent.			
<i>Reaction acidic.</i>			
Q	0	0.2	0.6
t	26	7	¼ min.
A	7	24	1 pt.

TABLE III.

Reaction alkaline.

0.372N-HCl.			0.43N-HCl.			0.5N-HCl.			0.59N-HCl.		
Q	t	A	Q	t	A	Q	t	A	Q	t	A
1.0	26 min.	43	1.0	7 min.	42	1.0	5 min.	30	1.0	6½ min.	17
1.2	8	53	1.2	3	49	1.2	2½	33	1.2	3½	23
		Ppt.			Ppt.	2.0	½	62	2.0	2	24

TABLE IV.

Reaction acidic.

0.75N-HCl.			1.53N-HCl.		
Q	t	A	Q	t	A
0	8 days	—		18 days	
0.05	12 min.	15	0.4	37 min.	17
0.1	6 „	24	0.5	18	29
0.2	3 „	37	0.6	9	44
0.3	10 sec.	70	0.7	3	65
0.4		Ppt.	0.8		Ppt.

It will be seen from Tables I-IV that pyridine has got a marked coagulating power both in the acid and the alkaline media. The time of setting of the gel decreases as the concentration of pyridine in the mixture is increased, till after a certain concentration no gel but a

mere flocculent precipitate is obtained. The increase in the quantity of pyridine in the mixture also increases the opacity of the gel.

It will also be seen from Table III that with the same quantity of pyridine the opacity of the gels formed from alkaline mixtures increases as the alkalinity of the mixtures is increased. It has been shown in Part I that in alkaline mixtures the gels obtained have larger molecular aggregates than in the acidic ones. It, therefore, appears that if the process of gelation is accelerated by a coagulant, the tendency of the alkaline mixture will be to give precipitates and not gels.

In the acid media on the other hand, the same amount of pyridine increases the time of setting as well as the transparency, with an increase in the acidity of the mixture.

Comparative Effect of Pyridine on the Setting of Mixtures of Solutions of Sodium Silicate and Organic and Inorganic Acids.

The comparative effect of pyridine on the setting of silicic acid gel from mixtures of sodium silicate solutions and nitric, hydrochloric and sulphuric acids and acetic, trichloroacetic, formic tartaric and citric acids from alkaline and acidic mixtures was then studied. The strengths of acids used in the acid and alkaline region were 1.46N and 0.486N respectively.

The time of setting with these mixtures, containing varying amounts of pyridine, was measured from the time-deflection curves. The results obtained are given in the following tables. The symbols used carry the same meaning as before.

TABLE V.

Reaction alkaline.

Q	...	0	0.8		1.0		1.2		2.0	
Acids.		t	t	A	t	A	t	A	t	A
			(min.)		(min.)		(min.)		(min.)	
Sulphuric	...	4 days	—	—	13	20.5	12	23	1	50
Hydrochloric	...	24 hrs. nearly	12	24	7	30	3	38		Ppt.
Nitric	...	„	12	25	6	31	2½	43		„

TABLE VI.

Reaction acidic.

Q	...	0	0.4		0.5		0.7	
Acids.		t	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A
Sulphuric	...	15 days	9	21	6	82		Ppt.
Hydrochloric		16	10	19	7	27		"
Nitric	...	21	13	14	8	27		"

TABLE VII.

Reaction alkaline.

Q	...	0	0.8		1.0		1.2		2.0	
Acids.		t	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A
Trichloroacetic	...	6 hrs.	8	42	3	48	1½	60	Ppt. in 30 sec.	
Acetic	...	7	8	29	3½	32	2½	38	" " " "	
Formic	...	—	9	27	4½	30	3	36	" " 40 "	
Tartaric	...	48	30	19	13	21	8	24	1	61
Citric	...	4 days			33	17	13	23	3	39

TABLE VIII.

Reaction acidic.

Q	...	0	0.4		0.5		0.7	
Acids.		t	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A		
Citric	...	12 hrs.	5½	42	2	60	Ppt. in 15 sec.	
Acetic	...	18 "	6½	35.5	3½	58	" " 30 "	
Tartaric	...	3 days	13	23	6½	37	Almost a stiff gel.	
Trichloroacetic	...	15 "	7	29	4	47.5	Ppt. in 45 sec.	
Formic	...	—	13	25	6½	35	Almost a stiff gel.	

It will be seen from Tables V-VIII that the effect of pyridine in all cases is one of coagulation. The order in which the time of setting is brought about by the same concentrations of mineral acids, with the same quantity of pyridine is sulphuric > hydrochloric > nitric in the acid and nearly nitric > hydrochloric > sulphuric in the alkaline one.

The same order is obtained with corresponding mixtures containing no pyridine in them. It is interesting to observe that the order of the acids obtained in the acid region is the order of their ionising power. It is to be expected, therefore, that the most highly ionised acid will normally delay the time of setting most. In the alkaline region the reverse order will be obtained.

With organic acids and pyridine the following order of behaviour is obtained in the acid and alkaline media respectively.

Citric > Acetic > Trichloroacetic > Formic > Tartaric;

Trichloroacetic > Acetic > Formic > Tartaric > Citric.

The same order has not been observed in the corresponding mixtures containing no pyridine in them.

The order of behaviour of the acids in the latter case is the same as that obtained by Holmes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, 22, 510) who worked chiefly with acid mixtures and concluded that the time of setting is partly dependent upon the number of hydrogen ions present in the mixture and suggested that the influence of ions other than the hydrogen ions on the setting of the gels may be considerable. The latter suggestion has been borne out in the present case by the behaviour of sulphuric acid in the alkaline region, as it takes a comparatively long time to bring about the setting, and by other slight abnormalities in the behaviour of the organic acids.

Effect of Alcohols and Acetone.

The effect of methyl, ethyl, and propyl alcohols and acetone on the time of setting of the gel-forming mixtures prepared from acidic ammonium acetate and acetic acid was next studied.

5 C.c. of ammonium acetate of double the strength required for the experiment were mixed with twice the required amount

of alcohols or acetone and the total volume was carefully made up to 10 c.c. by the addition of distilled water. 5 C.c. of this mixture were mixed with 5 c.c. of the four per cent. solution of sodium silicate in the manner already described. As sodium silicate is sparingly soluble in alcohols or acetone, higher concentrations of these substances could not be used. The time of setting with ammonium acetate was measured from the time-deflection curves and with acetic acid by Fleming's method.

The results obtained are given in the following tables:—

Q_1^* = c.c. of alcohol or acetone contained in 10 c.c. of the gel-forming mixtures.

TABLE IX.

Concentration of NH_4Ac = 5 per cent.

Reaction alkaline.

Q_1	CH_3OH		$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$		$\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$	
	t (mins.)	A	t (mins.)	A	t (min.)	A
0	$6\frac{1}{2}$	19	$6\frac{1}{2}$	19	$6\frac{1}{2}$	19
0.1	—	—	$4\frac{1}{2}$	20	3	20
0.25	$4\frac{1}{2}$	21	$3\frac{1}{2}$	21	2	22
0.5	$3\frac{1}{2}$	23	$2\frac{1}{2}$	24	$1\frac{1}{2}$	26
1.0	$1\frac{1}{2}$	26	35 sec.	38	15 sec.	50
2.0	$\frac{1}{2}$	40	—	—	—	—

TABLE X.

Reaction acidic.

Q_1^*	Conc. of NH_4Ac = 16.75 per cent.				Conc. of NH_4Ac = 20 per cent.			
	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$		$\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$		Q_1	CH_3OH		
	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A			t (min.)	A
0	15	10	15	10	0	22	7	
0.5	20	6	20	7	0.25	25	7	
1.0	—	—	22	6.5	1.0	36	5	
1.5	—	—	26	6	2.0	45	4	

TABLE XI.

Concentration of acetic acid = 0.486N.

Reaction alkaline.

Q ₁ *	CH ₃ OH <i>t</i>	C ₂ H ₅ OH <i>t</i>	C ₃ H ₇ OH <i>t</i>
0	7 hrs.	7 hrs.	7 hrs.
0.25	—	32 min.	29 min.
0.5	37 min.	8½ "	6½ "
1.0	5 "	50 sec.	35 sec.
1.5	2 "	5 "	4 "
2.0	Ppt.	Ppt.	Ppt.

TABLE XII.

Concentration of acetic acid = 0.82N

Reaction Acidic.

Q ₁ *	CH ₃ OH <i>t</i>	C ₂ H ₅ OH <i>t</i>	C ₃ H ₇ OH <i>t</i>
0	55 (min.)	55 (min.)	55 (min.)
0.5	71	88	88
1.0	—	125	115
2.0	—	180	—
2.5	155	—	—

TABLE XIII.

Strength of NH ₄ Ac.	Reaction.	0.25		Q ₁ *		1.0	
		A		A		A	
		<i>t</i> (min.)	<i>t</i>	<i>t</i> (min.)	<i>t</i>	<i>t</i> (min.)	<i>t</i>
16.75%	Acidic	14	7	15	7	22	6
4.0%	Alkaline	12	16	5	20	1	40

TABLE XIV.

Q ₁ *	0.75N-NH ₄ Ac. Reaction acidic. <i>t</i>	Q ₁ *	0.486N-HAc. Reaction alkaline. <i>t</i>
0	9½ min.	0	7 hrs.
0.5	19½	0.25	36 min.
1.0	30	1.0	1 "
2.0	62	1.5	7 sec.

It will be seen from the foregoing tables that increasing quantities of alcohol and acetone in the alkaline region not only decrease the time of setting but also increase the opacity of the gels.

The coagulating power of the alcohols increase with the increase in the CH_2 groups, that is $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} > \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} > \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$. Acetone has about the same coagulating action as ethyl alcohol.

When the gel-forming mixtures are even slightly acidic, alcohols as well as acetone act as protective agents and the time of setting is considerably delayed in their presence. The transparency of the gels is not much affected but in some cases a tendency to make them slightly more transparent has been observed.

Effect of Non-electrolytes on the Dialysed Sol of Silicic Acid.

Thomas Graham (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1864, 17, 321) found that alcohols, syrup of sugar and glycerine were among the inactive diluents of the pure sol of silicic acid. Pappada (*Gazzetta*, 1903, i, 35, 78, 86; *J. Chem. Soc., Abs.*, 1905, ii, 88, 387) found that alcohols, glycol, sucrose and many other sugars had neither any coagulant action on colloidal silica nor exerted any retarding influence on substances which cause coagulation.

The effect of pyridine, alcohols and acetone was examined on the pure sol of silicic acid, prepared by dialysing a mixture of sodium silicate and hydrochloric acid, and it was found that these substances did not coagulate the sol. The effect of these substances was then examined on the pure sol made alkaline and acidic by the addition of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid respectively. The results obtained are given in the following tables.

	TABLE XV.	
	Acid sol.	Alkaline sol.
Methyl alcohol	No action	Immediate coagulation.
Ethyl alcohol	"	"
Propyl alcohol	"	"
Acetone	"	"
Pyridine	"	"

Discussion of Results.

The behaviour of non-electrolytes on the setting of the silicic acid gel, when examined with reference to the nature of the medium in which it is formed, shows that there are two distinct effects: (i) That in an alkaline medium in which the colloidal particles of silicic acid carry a negative charge, the addition of the non-electrolytes decreases the time of setting or hastens the coagulation. (ii) That in a moderately acid medium where the particles are positively charged, the effect is to increase the time of setting or to exert a protective

influence on the colloidal particles. Pyridine is an exception to the above generalisation in that it hastens coagulation even in moderately acid mixtures.

The results obtained on the pure sol of silicic acid in the acid and alkaline media also indicate that the coagulation of the negatively charged sol takes place immediately by the addition of the non-electrolytes but the positive sol cannot be coagulated again, with the exception of pyridine. These results are similar to those of Klein (*Kolloid Z.*, 1921, 29, 247) who has found that negatively charged sols of arsenious sulphide, gold, silica and ferric oxide are agglomerated in part by alcohols whereas positively charged ferric oxide and silica are not.

The abnormalities observed above, both with the dialysed and the undialysed sols of silicic acid, cannot be explained on the diminution of the dielectric constant of the mixture and hence on the change in the density of the charge carried by the colloid particles, except that influences are all specific. Kruyt and van Duin (*Koll. Chem. Beihefte.*, 1914, 5, 287) were similarly unable to account for the fact that the same non-electrolyte stabilised a sol towards certain electrolytes and sensitised towards others.

Bilitzer (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 45, 312) found that a negatively charged platinum sol could be sensitised, discharged or even charged into a positive sol by the addition of suitable amounts of alcohol. It is probable in the present case, that the alcohols and acetone stabilise the positively charged silicic acid by increasing the density of the charge, though this point cannot be emphasised, in view of the scanty data available on this subject. Besides, the electric charge on the particles is not the only factor exerting an influence upon the probability of adhesion in the case of lyophilic sols and emulsoids. The electric charge of sols of agar-agar or gelatine can be taken away fully without causing the least indication of coagulation (*cf.* Kruyt and de Jong, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 100, 250; de Jong, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1924, 43, 189). The stability of these sols is maintained by the hydration of the colloid particles. The influence of hydration may also be an important factor on the stability of the highly hydrated positively charged particles of silicic acid in the acid medium, without prejudice, however, to the coagulating effect of the alcohols on the negatively charged particles, where other factors are evidently at work.